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Research Article

A Cross Sectional Interventional Study to Identify Drug Related Problem and Assess Patient Knowledge about Anti-Coagulant and Antiplatelet Agents at Tertiary Care Hospital in Dakshina Kannada

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ABSTRACT

Anticoagulants and antiplatelets are vital in treating cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) by preventing thrombus formation and embolic complications. However, they can cause adverse drug reactions (ADRs), particularly in geriatrics. Drug-drug interactions (DDIs) may lead to toxicity or reduced therapeutic effects. Patient education on risks and benefits improves adherence to treatment, impacting outcomes positively. To assess and identify DDIs and ADRs with the prescribed anticoagulant and antiplatelets and analyze the impact of education on patient knowledge on antiplatelets and anticoagulants. A cross-sectional interventional study was conducted among 150 participants based on the inclusion criteria. The data was collected by interviewing the patients or from patients' medical records and analyzed using Microsoft excel. Adverse drug reactions (ADRs) observed after administration of heparin were bleeding events in 6.89% of patients, including hematuria (3.4%) and upper gastrointestinal bleed (3.4%). Warfarin, acenocoumarol, dabigatran, and enoxaparin were associated with ADRs such as nosebleeds (12.5%), thrombocytopenia (33.3%), and abdominal pain (14.2%). Patients on aspirin, clopidogrel, and ticagrelor reported ADRs like dyspepsia (0.8%), melena (0.8%), and constipation (1.6%) which were managed with dose reduction or drug withdrawal. Additionally, the study identified eight drug-drug interactions, including clopidogrel with calcium channel blockers (moderate) and aspirin with acenocoumarol (major). Resolution included withholding interacting drugs and administering vitamin K. Post intervention patient knowledge was found to be improved. The study imparts demographic trends, comorbidities, and treatment patterns in patients receiving antiplatelet and anticoagulant therapy, explaining complex treatment regimens and low generic drug prescription rates. It highlights the need for standardized medication sourcing and comprehensive monitoring for optimized patient care. The study identified ADRs with anticoagulant and antiplatelet treatment, which were managed by adjusting

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doses or discontinuing drugs as needed. Patient awareness improved post-intervention notably for specific medications, with reduced uncertainty about treatment. The findings emphasize the need for vigilant management and patient education to enhance the safety and effectiveness of therapy.

INTRODUCTION

Anticoagulants and antiplatelets are among the most essential life-saving drugs that are generally used in cardiology for the prevention and treatment of many CVD such as ischemic heart disease, left ventricular dysfunction, acute coronary syndrome, valve abnormalities, atrial fibrillation, deep vein thrombosis, and pulmonary embolism. These drugs prevent thrombus extension and embolic complications by reducing the rate of fibrin formation. Antiplatelets are the root for prevention of arterial thrombosis, whereas anticoagulants are effective for venous thrombosis.[1] These drugs are either used orally (mostly for longterm therapy) or parenterally (for the prevention and initiation of treatment of thrombosis as well as other surgical procedures) and are among the most frequently implicated medications that cause ADRs in hospitalized patients, mostly elderly patients are at high risk to suffer from anticoagulant-associated ADRs such as ecchymosis, epistaxis, hematuria, gastro intestinal (GI) bleeding, thrombocytopenia, osteoporosis on long term use and hypersensitivity reactions. [2]

Multiple drugs are often required due to several comorbidities which turn out to be a barrier to get appropriate therapy. Drug-drug interaction (DDI) arises mostly whenever a patient receives more than one drug and chances increase with number of drugs taken. There are a variety of DDIs that can cause toxicity, alteration of the desired therapeutic effects or even result in a life-threatening condition. Drug-drug interactions is the one of major cause of adverse drug reactions (ADR) resulting in hospital and emergency department [3]

Thus, our present study focuses on the utilization pattern of antiplatelets and anticoagulants, assessment of compliance, prescription pattern, monitoring parameters, adverse reactions and drug interactions .[4]

Evidence indicates that collaborative decision-making with patients is crucial in the management of CVD Similarly, patients with CVD need to be appropriately informed about their disease and the use of oral anticoagulants. Oral anticoagulants are risk-prone drugs, and complex patient understanding is vital for promoting the rational use of oral anticoagulants. Moreover, knowledge of oral anticoagulant therapy can affect treatment outcomes in patients with CVD. Patients with better knowledge of the risk and benefit of oral anticoagulant therapy exhibit better adherence than those with inadequate knowledge [5].

OBJECTIVES

Assessment and identification of drug interaction and ADRs with the prescribed anticoagulant and antiplatelets

Analyze the impact of patient counselling on patient knowledge regarding antiplatelets and anticoagulants.

METHODOLOGY

Study Site: Srinivas Institute of Medical Science & Research Centre, Mukka, Mangalore

Study Type: Cross sectional interventional study

Study Duration: 2 months

Sample Size: 150^[14]

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients of age ranging from 18 to 90 years, belonging to both genders.

- Inpatients with or without comorbid conditions receiving antiplatelet or anticoagulant drugs.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Subjects who are unable to communicate such as severely ill patients, unconscious patients, and psychiatric patients
- Subjects who are not willing to participate

Methodology:

Study design: A cross-sectional interventional study was performed on drug utilization pattern in inpatients of various department in the Hospital. The study was completed in the period of 2 months at Srinivas Institute of Medical Science & Research Centre, Mukka, Mangalore.

Ethical Clearance: Ethical Clearance was from the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) of Srinivas Institute of Medical Science and Research Centre (SIMS & RC), Mukka, Mangalore.

Data Collection:

- Data collection form includes patient's demographic details, past medical and medication history, current medications given, any DRPs found in prescription and lab parameters, includes questionnaires regarding knowledge on antiplatelets and anticoagulants
- Patient selection: The patients for the study was selected based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria.
- Obtaining inform consent: During the hospital visit, we explained to the study participants about the study and obtained consent for collecting data.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Profile of antiplatelets and anticoagulation adverse effects

Table 1: Profile of antiplatelets and anticoagulation adverse effects

SR.NO	Drug	Type of ADRs	No of patients (%)	Total no of patients (%)
1	Heparin (n=29)	Haematuria UGI bleed	1 (3.4%) 1 (3.4%)	2(6.89%)
2	Warfarin (n=8)	Nose bleeding	1 (12.5%)	1(12.5%)
3	Acenocoumarol (n=3)	Thrombocytopenia	1(33.3%)	1(33.3%)
4	Dabigatran (n=7)	Abdominal pain Allergic reaction Heart burn	1(14.2%) 1(14.2%) 1(14.2%)	3(42.85)
5	Enoxaparin (n=9)	Bruising Nose bleeding	1(11.1%) 1(11.1%)	2(22.2%)
6	Aspirin (n=125)	Dyspepsia Blood in stools Constipation haematuria	1(0.8%) 1(0.8%) 2(1.6%) 2(1.6%)	6(4.8%)
7	Clopidogrel (n=41)	Diarrhoea Rash	1(2.43%) 1(2.43%)	2(4.87%)
8	Ticagrelor (n=3)	Dyspnoea	1(33.3%)	1(33.3%)

2. Drugs causing ADR based on Naranjo Algorithm causality scale

Table 2: Drugs causing ADR based on Naranjo Algorithm causality scale

Adverse effects	Score	Causality
Heparin induced haematuria	3	Possible
Heparin induced UGI bleed	2	Possible
Warfarin induced Nose bleeding	3	Possible
Acenocoumarol induced Thrombocytopenia	5	Probable
Dabigatran induced Abdominal pain	4	Possible
Dabigatran induced Allergic reaction	3	Possible
Dabigatran induced Heart burn	3	Possible
Enoxaparin induced Bruising	2	Possible
Enoxaparin induced Nose bleeding	3	Possible
Aspirin induced Dyspepsia	2	Possible
Aspirin induced Blood in stools	5	Probable
Aspirin induced Constipation	2	Possible
	3	Possible
Aspirin induced haematuria	5	Probable
	2	Possible
Clopidogrel induced Diarrhoea	2	Possible
Clopidogrel induced rash	2	Possible
Ticagrelor induced dyspnoea	3	Possible

Out of 29 patients administered with heparin, 2 patients (6.89%) suffered from bleeding events such as haematuria 1(3.4%), UGI bleed 1(3.4%), Haematuria refers to blood in the urine, while UGI bleeds are bleeds that occur in the upper part of the gastrointestinal tract, which includes the esophagus, stomach, and duodenum. These adverse effects are important to monitor and manage, particularly in patients receiving anticoagulant therapy. Out of 8 patients who were administered with warfarin, 1 patient suffered from nosebleed. Among 3 patients administered with acenocoumarol, 1 patient suffered from thrombocytopenia (i.e platelet count less than 61000cells/cmm). Among 7 patients administered with dabigatran, 1 patient (14.2%) suffered from abdominal pain, allergic reaction, heart burn. Among 9 patients administered with enoxaparin 1(11.1%) patient suffered from bruising and nose bleed. These adverse effects are important to

monitor and manage, particularly in patients receiving anticoagulant therapy

Out of 125 patients administered with aspirin ,1(0.8%) patient suffered from dyspepsia, blood in stools, 2 (1.6%) suffered from constipation and hematuria. Among 41 administered with clopidogrel ,1 (2.43%) patient suffered from diarrhea and rash. Among participants administered with ticagrelor 1 (33.3%) patient suffered from dyspnea. This adverse reaction was resolved by dose reduction or withholding/withdrawing the drug. The causality assessment for ADRs were analyzed using Naranjo scale and out of 18 ADRs, 15 were possible and 3 were probable.

3. Clinically significant drug-drug interactions of antiplatelets and anticoagulants

Table 3: Clinically significant drug-drug interactions of antiplatelets and anticoagulants

Sr.No	Drug Interaction	severity	Interaction
1	Clopidogrel \diamond Amlodipine	Moderate	CCB diminishes the therapeutic effect of clopidogrel
2	Aspirin \diamond Acenocoumarol	Major	Aspirin enhances the anticoagulation effect of acenocoumarol
3	Clopidogrel \diamond Esomeprazole	Major	Co-administration of clopidogrel with PPI decreases cardio protective effect of clopidogrel
4	Aspirin \diamond Losartan	Moderate	Serum potassium level of the patient was increased
5	Inj.Heparin \diamond Aspirin	Moderate	Aspirin enhances the anticoagulation effect of heparin
6	Inj.Heparin \diamond nitroglycerin	Moderate	Nitro-glycerine decreases effect of heparin
7	Aspirin \diamond dabigatran	Major	Aspirin enhances the adverse effects of dabigatran etexilate (risk for bleeding may be increased)
8	Aspirin \diamond clopidogrel	Moderate	Increases the toxicity of others by pharmacodynamic changes

The patients medication chart was evaluated for drug interaction involving anticoagulants and antiplatelet therapy. A total of 8 interactions were identified, in which 1 interaction each was found between clopidogrel and calcium channel blockers (moderate), aspirin and acenocoumarol (major), clopidogrel and proton pump inhibitor (major), aspirin and angiotensin receptor blockers (moderate), Inj. heparin and aspirin (moderate), Inj. heparin and vasodilators (moderate), aspirin

and dabigatran (major) and between aspirin and clopidogrel (moderate). The various resolutions done were withholding the interacting drugs and administration of vitamin k. In some patients no change in drug therapy was observed. The various drug-drug interactions were assessed using lexicodugs.

4. Knowledge of Patients regarding antiplatelets and anticoagulant therapy

Figure 1: Assessing the knowledge of the patient regarding name of the drug

Prior to the intervention or education, only 13.3% of participants were aware that they were taking antiplatelet and anticoagulant drugs, while the majority (86.6%) were not aware. However, after the study, awareness dramatically increased to

100%, with all 150 participants acknowledging that they were taking these medications. This significant shift indicates the effectiveness of the study in educating participants about their medication regimen.

Figure 2: Assessing the knowledge of patient about prescribed medicine

In Pre-study, 7.7% of respondents indicated they did not know the reason for the prescription, which decreased to 0% post-study, indicating a significant improvement in understanding. Overall, the post-study results show a substantial improvement in respondents' understanding of the

reasons for prescribing the medicine, with fewer respondents indicating uncertainty and more accurately identifying conditions such as cardiac issues/chest pain and cerebrovascular accidents as reasons for the prescription

Figure 3: Evaluating patients' understanding of how medications function within their bodies.

In Pre-study, 86.8% of respondents indicated they did not know how the medicine works in the body, which decreased significantly to 4.6% post-study, indicating a remarkable improvement in understanding. The majority of respondents (9.9% pre-study, 94.7% post-study) correctly identified that the medicine prevents blood clotting, showing

a substantial increase in understanding. Overall, the post-study results show a significant enhancement in respondents' understanding of how the medicine works in the body, with a vast majority correctly identifying its role in preventing blood clotting.

Figure 4: Assessing how frequently do need to consume this medication each day

In Pre-study, 66.2% of respondents indicated they did not know how many times a day the medicine needed to be taken, which decreased dramatically to 1.3% post-study, indicating a substantial improvement in understanding. Overall, the post-study results show a remarkable enhancement in respondents' understanding of the frequency of taking the medicine, with a vast majority correctly

identifying that it needs to be taken once a day. There was also a significant decrease in the percentage of respondents indicating uncertainty regarding the dosing frequency.

4.1 Knowledge of Patients regarding antiplatelets and anticoagulant therapy

Table 4: Knowledge of Patients regarding antiplatelets and anticoagulant therapy

SR. NO	QUESTIONS	RESPONSE	CASE GROUP		CONTROL GROUP		P value
			PRE (n=64)	POST (n=64)	PRE (n=64)	POST (n=64)	
1	How does this medicine work in your body?	a. Lowers BP	5 (7.8%)	4 (6.25%)	10 (15.6%)	9 (14%)	<.00001
		b. lowers heart rate	9 (14%)	3 (4.6%)	6 (9.3%)	5 (0.7%)	
		c. Prevents blood from clotting	15 (23.4%)	41 (64%)	17 (26.5%)	19 (29.6%)	
		d. Do not know	35 (54.6%)	16 (25%)	31 (48.4%)	31 (48.4%)	
2	Why is it Important to Take this medicine exactly as your doctor has told you?	a. Too much of this can cause bleeding	9 (14%)	29 (45%)	14 (21.8%)	15 (23.4%)	<.00001
		b. It interacts with food, so changing the dose/ timing can be hazardous	11 (17.1%)	26 (40.6%)	2 (3.1%)	4 (6.2%)	
		c. Do not know	44 (68.7%)	9 (14%)	48 (75%)	45 (70.3%)	
3	Is it important to take this medicine at the same time each day?	a. Yes	11 (17.1%)	44 (68.7%)	21 (32.8%)	22 (34.3%)	<.00001
		b. No	23 (35.9%)	9 (14%)	7 (10.9%)	9 (14%)	

		c. Not sure	30 (46.8%)	11 (17.1%)	36 (56.2%)	33 (51.5%)	
4	Is it okay to double the next dose of this medicine if you miss a dose?	a. Yes	18 (28.1%)	8 (12.5%)	32 (50%)	31 (48.4%)	<.00001
		b. No	14 (21.8%)	51 (79.6%)	20 (31.2%)	22 (34.3%)	
		c. Not sure	32 (50%)	5 (7.8%)	12 (18.7%)	11 (17.1%)	
5	Is it possible that skipping one dose of this medicine could worsen your condition?	a. Yes	27 (42.1%)	20 (31.2%)	35 (54.6%)	34 (21.8%)	<.00001
		b. No	11 (17.1%)	30 (46.8%)	14 (21.8%)	16 (25%)	
		c. Not sure	26 (40.6%)	14 (21.8%)	15 (23.4%)	14 (61.7%)	
6	Is it appropriate to stop taking this medicine once you feel better?	a. Yes	28 (43.7%)	14 (21.8%)	41 (64%)	40 (62.5%)	<.00001
		b. No	10 (15.6%)	39 (60.9%)	12 (18.7%)	13 (20.3%)	
		c. Not sure	26 (40.6%)	11 (17.1%)	11 (17.1%)	11 (17.1%)	
7	Is it safe to take anti-inflammatory medicines like ibuprofen (Nurofen® or Advil®) while you are taking this medicine?	a. Yes	18 (28.1%)	15 (23.4%)	37 (57.8%)	33 (51.5%)	<.00001
		b. No	12 (18.7%)	35 (54.6%)	10 (15.6%)	12 (18.7%)	
		c. Not sure	34 (53.1%)	14 (21.8%)	17 (26.5%)	19 (29.6%)	
8	Is it safe to take vitamin supplements and herbal medicines with this medicine without consulting your doctor?	a. Yes	38 (59.3%)	15 (23.4%)	38 (59.3%)	35 (54.6%)	<.00001
		b. No	11 (17.1%)	37 (57.8%)	10 (15.6%)	12 (18.7%)	
		c. Not sure	15 (23.4%)	12 (18.7%)	16 (25%)	17 (60.7%)	
9	Is there any benefit in taking more of this medicine than your doctor has told you to take?	a. Yes	25 (39%)	16 (25%)	48 (75%)	46 (71.8%)	<.00001
		b. No	11 (17.1%)	45 (70.3%)	15 (23.4%)	16 (25%)	
		c. Not sure	28 (43.7%)	3 (4.6%)	3 (4.6%)	6 (9.3%)	
10	Will drinking too much alcohol increase the risk of side effects with this medicine?	a. Yes	10 (15.6%)	39 (60.9%)	23 (35.9%)	24 (37.5%)	<.00001
		b. No	54 (84.3%)	25 (39%)	31 (48.4%)	40 (62.5%)	
11	Would you Inform a surgeon, dentist or other health professional that you are taking this medicine before undergoing surgery or procedure?	a. Yes	12 (18.7%)	44 (68.7%)	19 (29.6%)	21 (32.8%)	<.00001
		b. No	52 (81.2%)	20 (31.2%)	45 (70.3%)	43 (67.1%)	
12	Three signs of side effects that you should watch out for while taking this medicine are	a. Bleeding gums	7 (10.9%)	22 (34.3%)	12 (18.7%)	13 (20.3%)	<.00001
		b. Blood in urine	8 (12.5%)	15 (44.1%)	3 (4.6%)	3 (4.6%)	

		c. Prolonged nosebleeds	5 (7.8%)	13 (20.3%)	6 (9.3%)	7 (10.9%)	
		d. Insomnia	15 (23.4%)	0	11 (17.1%)	11 (17.1%)	
		e. Severe bruising	2 (3.1%)	14 (21.8%)	5 (7.8%)	5 (7.8%)	
		f. Loss of appetite	11 (17.1%)	0	1 (1.5%)	2 (3.1%)	
		g. Do not know	16 (25%)	0	26 (40.6%)	23 (35.9%)	
13	Three things you can do to reduce your risk of side effects are:	a. Monitor INR regularly	1 (1.5%)	11 (17.1%)	3 (4.6%)	4 (6.2%)	<.00001
		b. Monitor side effects	8 (12.5%)	22 (34.3%)	11 (17.1%)	12 (18.7%)	
		c. Sleeping on time	17 (26.5%)	0	16 (25%)	15 (23.4%)	
		d. Eating less food	14 (21.8%)	0	6 (9.3%)	6 (9.3%)	
		e. Avoid things that could cause cuts/ injuries	3 (4.6%)	13 (20.3%)	8 (12.5%)	9 (14%)	
		f. Proper dosing	3 (4.6%)	18 (28.1%)	6 (9.3%)	6 (9.3%)	
		g. Do not know	18 (28.1%)	0	14 (21.8%)	14 (21.8%)	
14	What is the best step to take if you accidentally take too much of this medicine?	a. Skip the next dose	11 (17.1%)	19 (29.6%)	11 (17.1%)	12 (18.7%)	<.00001
		b. Consult my doctor	8 (12.5%)	32 (50%)	11 (17.1%)	11 (17.1%)	
		c. Be alert for signs of side effects	9 (14%)	11 (17.1%)	6 (9.3%)	7 (10.9%)	
		d. Do not know	36 (56.2%)	2 (3.1%)	36 (56.2%)	34 (53.1%)	
15	Is it possible for what you eat to affect your anticoagulant or antiplatelet therapy?	a. Yes	13 (20.3%)	40 (62.5%)	18 (28.1%)	19 (29.6%)	<.00001
		b. No	20 (31.2%)	14 (21.8%)	32 (50%)	31 (48.4%)	
		c. Not sure	31 (48.4%)	10 (15.6%)	14 (21.8%)	14 (21.8%)	

150 participants were surveyed to assess their knowledge about antiplatelets and anticoagulants.

The assessment consisted of 15 questions where based on the scoring system 22(14.6%) demonstrated good knowledge about antiplatelets and anticoagulants while 128(85.3%) lacked it;

subsequently, the participants with less knowledge were divided into two groups, with 64(50%) in the first and 64 (50%) in the second, the latter of which received an intervention and former was kept as control.

After the intervention, the case group showed a marked improvement in knowledge about how the

medicine works, the importance of adhering to prescribed dosages, and the necessity of taking the medication at the same time each day. They also gained a better grasp of the consequences of missing doses, including the risks of worsening their condition, and the inappropriateness of stopping the medication early once feeling better. Additionally, their awareness increased regarding potential interactions with other drugs, alcohol, and supplements. The case group became more adept at identifying side effects and knowing the correct steps to take if too much medication is accidentally consumed. In contrast, the control group's knowledge remained relatively unchanged, highlighting the effectiveness of the intervention in improving medication-related knowledge. In this data, p-value is less than 0.00001 across various questions indicate that the intervention effectively improved the case group's understanding of their medication compared to the control group. p-value suggests that the differences observed in the case group compared to the control group are highly statistically significant. It indicates a strong likelihood that the intervention caused the changes in knowledge.

DISCUSSION

This study indicates a significant incidence of ADRs among patients receiving anticoagulant and antiplatelet therapy. Among the subjects, Heparin administration resulted in bleeding events in 6.89% of patients, bleeding events were most commonly observed ADR, with variations in the specific types of bleeding reported, such as gastrointestinal bleeds(possible) and nosebleeds(possible). Management strategies for ADRs also aligned, with dose adjustments and drug discontinuation being common approaches. This is similar to the study carried out by Vijayakumar T M et al. in which bleeding events were the most commonly observed ADRs [2].

In the present study out of 150 cases 9 ADRs were found in patients taking antiplatelets, out of which 6 were associated with aspirin, like aspirin induced dyspepsia(possible), melena (probable), constipation(possible) hematuria(probable) ,2 were associated with clopidogrel like clopidogrel induced diarrhea(possible) and rash(possible) and 1 with ticagrelor like ticagrelor induced dyspnea(possible). This is similar to the study carried out by Reddy R P et al, in which bleeding events were the most commonly observed ADRs [1].

In this study, out of 150 patients 8 interactions were identified, highlighting the complexity of managing multiple medications in patients with CVDs. On analysis common interaction was seen between aspirin and clopidogrel which was linked to an increased risk of bleeding followed by other combinations such as clopidogrel with calcium channel blockers and aspirin with acenocoumarol. These interactions pose risks of either increasing toxicity or reducing therapeutic efficacy, underscoring the importance of vigilant monitoring and medication reconciliation, this is similar to the study carried out by Reddy R P et al., Resolutions included withholding interacting drugs and administering vitamin K [1].

This study carried out the intervention which focused on patient education and yielded promising results in improving medication knowledge and adherence. During pre-intervention, there was a lack of awareness among patients regarding their medications, whereas during post-intervention, there was a notable improvement in understanding specific medications, dosing regimens, and reasons for prescription. This is similar to the study carried out by Alajami HN et al., in which there was a significant improvement in medication knowledge

and adherence post-study regarding their medication [4].

CONCLUSION

The study focused on adverse effects, drug interactions, and patient awareness related to anticoagulant and antiplatelet therapies. It observed significant occurrences of bleeding among patients receiving anticoagulants, stressing the need for rigorous monitoring and management strategies. Identified drug interactions necessitated interventions such as discontinuing interacting drugs to mitigate risks. Patient awareness regarding medications, including Dabigatran, Warfarin, and Enoxaparin, notably improved following the study, indicating enhanced understanding of dosing and potential side effects. Awareness regarding antiplatelet drugs also increased, with fewer patients uncertain about their prescriptions and better grasp of medication dosing schedules. The study highlighted the effectiveness of patient education in improving medication management practices, emphasizing the importance of informed patient involvement to optimize safety and treatment outcomes in anticoagulant and antiplatelet therapies.

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